

NEW PERSPECTIVES ON MEDICAL TEACHING

Yuldoshev Murodkhan Khusanovich
Elliev Javokhir Abdirashidovich
Abdujabborov Islom Akhrorovich

Residents of the Department of Traumatology and Orthopedics

Scientific adviser: Makhmatkulov O.Kh.

Samarkand State Medical University

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Annotation: the thesis provides data on new teaching methods, including in the field of medicine. The latest developments in this area and its use in the field of traumatology and orthopedics are discussed.

Keywords: Moodle, gamification, distance learning, webinars, interactive technology, education.

The relevance of the research topic is due to the fact that today technologies have a significant impact on the field of education, providing opportunities for improving the communication process and using the latest information systems in education [1]. In the context of the development of the information society, a transformation of educational approaches is taking place: traditional approaches based on the transmission of knowledge are becoming a thing of the past and new ones based on the use of information, communication and gaming technologies are emerging.

This is largely due to the technologization of modern society and the change of generations. The generation of "digital natives" (from the English digital natives, according to M. Prensky) is used to perceiving information very quickly, they like to do several things at the same time, they prefer the visual presentation of information to its textual presentation, they are used to receiving instant feedback and constant encouragement in the form of awards and give preference to games rather than "serious" business [2]. Representatives of the new, "digital" generation are challenging traditional approaches and models in the education system.

Purpose: evaluate new methods of teaching in the field of medicine.

The global trend towards digitalization of all areas of society's life has led to changes affecting the field of vocational education. Today, the work of a teacher is partially compensated by technology, requiring knowledge and skills in the field of digitalization. New competencies appear, a new personnel potential of education, new educational concepts are being formed. Educational standards have increased the requirements for the organization and quality of vocational education. However, education lags behind modern realities, remaining conservative in its essence. Actualization of activities and tasks in the system of vocational education indicates the need to improve the quality of training of graduates and improve the educational process.

We analyzed the games Biotopia, Physicus and Chemicus, which are designed to explore the corresponding subjects in the game content. Due to the fact that access to gamified programs is carried out via the Internet or other networks, students were not tied to a specific place and time, they could move through the material at their own pace from any part of the globe. In addition, it allows them to acquire knowledge in a more accessible and easy way. They will not be afraid to make mistakes and can easily work on mistakes, and the game sphere will involve them in this process, which will increase their concentration. We are all familiar with

such gamified programs as “Healthy lifestyle”, “Samsung health”, “Proper nutrition”, “Drink water”, “Fitness”, etc., which are available in all smartphones and count steps taken, water drunk, physical activity, caloric value of the diet and much more. Studies have shown that since the use of these programs, good habits in the form of adherence to the drinking regime, diet, sports, activity during the day have increased in people than before using them. This is also a confirmation of the effectiveness of gamification.

Gamification is today recognized as one of the most effective approaches to teaching through effective staff management with student involvement in the learning environment. So, since 2011, gamification has been actively developing: there has been an increase in scientific publications on gamification, especially abroad, the first analytical reviews began to appear, which described the process of formation and popularization of gamification tools in educational processes. The gamification of the learning process is focused on the joint work of both students within the group and with the teacher. The system provides a lot of tools for this: wiki, glossary, blogs, forums, workshops, levels. The system supports the exchange of files of any format - both between the teacher and the student, and between the students themselves. In addition, the main element of gamification is the levels and rewards in them. As a reward for successful work, points are awarded to students, certificates are issued in the gaming environment, with group participation it is possible to highlight the dignity of each participant with "medals" such as "the fastest answer", "the best in the know", "the most creative approach" and much more. All this, of course, is the advantage of this platform, which provides full-fledged training in any field. Due to the fact that in addition to textual material, gamification uses audio, video, animation, diagrams, various glossaries and workshops, in a word, visual material, it helps a comprehensive study of the topic, the development of thinking and the ability to memorize with the help of associations.

As a result of the implementation of this project in 2011, 80 university facilities were connected to the network. In 2012, 84 objects of the system of secondary specialized and vocational education were connected to the unified corporate network of "Electronic Education". Since July 25, 2012, a modernly equipped Center for the implementation of e-learning in educational institutions under the MHSSE has been operating, founded in accordance with the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers. These data show how important for our country is the development of technologies in the field of education, as well as the training of highly qualified personnel. There is a lot of research going on in the field of gamification at the moment, and we have not been left behind.

Conclusions: Based on the above, we can say that gamification is one of the advanced technologies and meets all the needs of students. At this stage, both in our country and abroad, there are no gamified subjects in many disciplines, including the disciplines of medical universities.

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